

THE CORPUS-BASED APPROACH: ENHANCING LANGUAGE LEARNING THROUGH AUTHENTIC RESOURCES

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Annotation This article explores the significance of the corpus-based approach in language learning and teaching. It discusses the concept of a corpus as a collection of authentic texts that represents a language or linguistic variant. The corpus-based approach focuses on utilizing these texts to provide learners with genuine language examples and patterns. The article also highlights the impact of corpus linguistics on learner autonomy and the development of authentic teaching resources. It emphasizes the role of the corpus-based approach in addressing specific language learning needs, such as improving vocabulary and grammar skills in writing tasks. Overall, the article underscores the value of incorporating corpus-based activities in language instruction to enhance the quality of learning materials and promote effective language acquisition.

Keywords: corpus, language learning, authentic resources, corpus-based approach, native speakers, language acquisition, academic discourse, student-centered learning, EFL learners, vocabulary, grammar

Аннотация В этой статье исследуется значение корпусного подхода в изучении и преподавании языка. В нем обсуждается концепция корпуса как собрания аутентичных текстов, представляющих язык или лингвистический вариант. Подход, основанный на корпусе, фокусируется на использовании этих текстов, чтобы предоставить учащимся подлинные языковые примеры и модели. В статье также подчеркивается влияние корпусной лингвистики на самостоятельность учащихся и развитие аутентичных учебных ресурсов. В нем подчеркивается роль корпусного подхода в удовлетворении конкретных

потребностей в изучении языка, таких как улучшение словарного запаса и грамматических навыков при выполнении письменных заданий. В целом, в статье подчеркивается ценность включения корпусных занятий в обучение языку для повышения качества учебных материалов и содействия эффективному овладению языком.

Ключевые слова: корпус, изучение языка, аутентичные ресурсы, корпусный подход, носители языка, овладение языком, академический дискурс, личностно-ориентированное обучение, учащиеся EFL, словарный запас, грамматика

Language learning is a dynamic process that requires exposure to real-world usage and authentic resources. In recent years, the corpus-based approach has emerged as a powerful tool in language instruction, enabling learners to engage with genuine language as it is spoken and written by native speakers in various contexts. This article explores the significance of corpus linguistics in language teaching, its impact on learner autonomy, and its potential to improve the quality of learning materials. A corpus is a collection of texts that represents a language or linguistic variant. It comprises texts generated in real-world settings, including publications, dialogs, emails, articles, and presentations, making it an accurate reflection of natural language. The corpus-based approach leverages this extensive collection of language data to provide learners with authentic examples and usage patterns.

Corpus linguistics has gained prominence as an exponentially advancing discipline within modern linguistics. By offering a ready supply of original texts for language acquisition, it enables learners to study the linguistic characteristics of written and spoken academic discourse. This approach has paved the way for the development of more authentic teaching resources, frequency-based dictionaries, and ESL materials, such as books, that cater to learners' needs.

One of the primary reasons the corpus-based approach is highly engaging and efficient is its ability to provide students with information and sources that enhance their understanding and perceptual learning capabilities. By immersing learners in a

large volume of authentic language, the corpus method equips them with the tools to become autonomous learners. Teachers play a crucial role as supervisors in this student-centered learning process, guiding learners as they explore linguistic rules and trends through data-driven learning (DDL).

In the context of private language teaching centers, where instructors have the flexibility to choose teaching methods based on learners' needs, the corpus-based approach proves particularly valuable. For instance, when teaching adult English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners preparing for the International English Language Testing System (IELTS) exam, this approach can address common challenges in writing Task 1 reports, such as grammar and vocabulary.

By implementing corpus-based activities, teachers can effectively target these issues and advance learners' vocabulary and grammar skills in IELTS Task 1 essays. This article aims to share the results of implementing corpus-based activities in a private language teaching center and how these practices can help overcome linguistic barriers in learners' writing. Furthermore, it underscores the importance of continuous professional development for teachers, who strive to enhance their pedagogical competence and the quality of instruction.

In conclusion, the corpus-based approach offers a wealth of benefits in language learning by providing learners with authentic resources and promoting learner autonomy. Through the exploration of real-world language data, students can develop a deeper understanding of linguistic patterns and rules. For teachers, embracing the corpus-based approach enhances their teaching repertoire, enabling them to create engaging and effective learning experiences. By harnessing the power of the corpus, language educators can unlock the full potential of their students and facilitate their language learning journey.